

Enhancing Circular Nutrient Flows with Biofertilizers: Feasibility Studies and Regional Insights from the P2GREEN Project

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This paper presents the Horizon Europe P2Green project's current research findings and projected outcomes. The project is testing four innovative technologies in Germany, Sweden, and Spain to convert human sanitary waste into safe, bio-based fertilizers for agriculture. The paper outlines the progress of these pilot technologies, initial field trial results, and confirms that the bio-based fertilizers are both safe and efficient compared to conventional chemical alternatives. It also discusses policy and governance considerations for scaling these technologies within the pilot regions and across the EU. The P2Green project is also exploring the feasibility of expanding these technologies to Italy, Hungary, France, and Greece, where three distinct feasibility studies are underway. These studies are critical for assessing the regional potential for implementing the technologies. Initial phases of the feasibility studies, focusing on data collection, have begun. Insights from these studies are vital for evaluating the adaptability and effectiveness of technologies in diverse settings. Expert consultations, including focus groups and workshops, show strong support for implementing these bio-based fertilizers, despite challenges like implementation costs.

In the Greek region, three case studies have been identified. The Agricultural University of Athens is conducting a feasibility study on implementing Vuna Nexus's urine treatment technology on its campus. T.O.E.V Tavropou, responsible for land reclamation management in Karditsa, is implementing BioAzul's water reclamation technology. Additionally, Goldeimer's urine separation technology will be implemented in collaboration with a Greek toilet rental company, using dry toilets for large events, such as festivals. This paper reviews the preliminary work and potential agricultural benefits, as well as the next steps for these feasibility studies.

Keywords: circular nutrient flows; farm to fork; air and water pollution control, fertilizer, wastewater management; feasibility studies

1. Introduction

Nutrient losses in the environment are a major threat to the functioning of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) flows are considered the most critical, as high N & P loads are associated with problems such as groundwater pollution, eutrophication and loss of biodiversity (too much to lose). The agri-food sector plays a key role as it is significantly contributing to N & P pollution on the one hand but at the same time the agricultural production in Europe depends on mineral fertilizers, with an estimated consumption of approximately 11 million tons N & P per year (*Eurostat*). Mineral N fertilizers (the most used nutrient in the EU in terms of volume) result from energy-intensive industrial processes that are heavily dependent on fossil fuels (for energy use and as a feedstock) and are a major source of industrial and agricultural emissions in the EU. The current production methods for N & P fertilizer are not sustainable and the mineral P fertilizers are sourced outside of the EU and often mined under precarious and unsustainable conditions (Vermeulen et al., 2012). Furthermore, the supplies of N & P are not guaranteed due to increased costs and limited supplies. Higher energy prices impact N fertilizer production and the world's P reserves may be exhausted at the end of the 21st century if today's fertilization practices continue. Together, these factors challenge the EU's food security. Moreover, nutrient losses of N & P include diffuse emissions from agriculture and point emissions from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs.) (Desmit et al., 2018). The intensive use of fertilizers in agricultural production is a major factor for N & P pollution. High nutrient concentrations are also found in human sanitary waste streams from where they are ultimately released to rivers and coastal zones, including effluxes from WWTPs. Nutrient removal in WWTPs is very energy intensive and in modern WWTPs not all N can be removed from wastewater. The removed N ultimately ends up in the atmosphere as molecular nitrogen (N₂) and to a lower share as the very potent greenhouse gas nitrous oxide (N₂O). For P, only 34% of WWTP inputs are recycled by spreading sewage sludge on agricultural fields. The use of sewage sludge for fertilization, however, is connected to problems such as micro pollutants, which are rarely removed by WWTPs (Gianico et al., 2021).

2. Overview of the P2GREEN project.

P2Green's goal is to develop the nutrient cycle between urban settings with high levels of nutrients in wastewater (blue infrastructure) and rural areas with a high demand of nutrients for agricultural production (green infrastructure). Various innovative and safe approaches have been developed to efficiently recover nutrients from human excreta. However, these have yet to be scaled up to fulfil their true potential. About 3.1 Tg (i.e. 109 kg) N and 0.6 Tg P are excreted every year by the EU's population, corresponding to 30% and 55% of the number of mineral fertilisers applied on agricultural fields in the EU. P2Green addresses this potential and will transform nutrient streams on a regional level to close N & P cycles from sanitation (via new bio-based fertilisers) to agricultural production (from waste to farm to fork). To facilitate systemic change, co-creation strategies including the participation of all relevant stakeholders, (Larsen et al., 2013) as well as harmonised governance frameworks that foster innovations will be key to P2Green. Collaborative innovation networks of technology provider, industry, farmers, scientific communities, public administration and citizens will help maximise the value

of knowledge production, circulation and use of the project's transformative approaches. The involvement of local municipalities and regional governments as well as the interaction with policy makers on the national and EU level will also be a key part of P2Green.

P2Green's envisaged transformation (Fig. 1) will (i) reduce municipal waste streams, thereby helping to achieve the 2030 targets of the EU's Zero Pollution Action Plan, the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) and Sewage Sludge Directive (SSD); (ii) increase self-sufficiency of P in the EU; (iii) save water resources ; (iv) reduce harmful production practices of mineral fertilisers; (v) reduce nutrient losses of N & P; (vi) enable tailored fertilisers, reducing nutrient loss further; (vii) minimise cropland expansion through optimal fertiliser use increasing yield on the existing agricultural area¹⁷; (viii) open new market potentials for bio-based fertilisers, and (ix) simultaneously enable micropollutants such as pharmaceutical residues or hormones to be more easily removed. Overall, the circular systems will help to increase sustainability and resilience of the agri-food system and will contribute to the EU objectives on reducing nutrient losses by 50% until 2050.

Figure 1. P2Green's envisaged transformation to circular nutrient streams in Europe.

To achieve its objectives, P2Green will draw upon innovative technological approaches to efficiently recover nutrients from human excreta close to source and will further develop these approaches in 3 pilot regions towards multi-sectoral circular governance solutions where discarded N & P from urban sanitary systems become a valuable resource. This will be done through the implementation of 4 different "waste-recycling technologies for the agri-food value chain by reusing sanitary waste as bio-based fertilisers, thus closing N & P nutrient cycles between rural and urban environments.

2.1 Methodology

The EU funded project, P2Green adopts a comprehensive, circular approach emphasizing the scaling of four innovative technologies and focusing on the creation of circular business models, active stakeholders' involvement across the value chain. Additionally, tries to engage policy makers and to establish governance models to

facilitate a transformation of the nutrient system. This concept will be tested and demonstrated in three pilot regions in Spain, Sweden and Germany. The use of recycled fertilizers in P2GreeN aligns with the Farm to fork strategy that aims to limit the fertilizers use to sustainable levels by adhering to regional guidelines. This includes determining the nutrient content of soils prior to fertilization as far as possible. If the nutrient composition of recycled fertilizers is insufficient to meet crop demands without causing an excess of a particular nutrient, additional nutrients will be supplemented using mineral fertilizers. Modern and efficient fertilization techniques will be applied to minimize environmental impacts, like nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) leaching, as well as gaseous nitrogen emissions:

1. Urea fertilisers used for barley cultivation in the Swedish pilot region will be incorporated into soil during sowing to limit N losses from ammonia emissions and leaching. Further measures such as the use of nitrification inhibitors to reduce nitrate leaching and nitrous oxide emissions will be considered as well.
2. N and P fertilisation in the German pilot region will be done according to the German Fertilising Ordinance, which already sets strict limits to reduce nutrient pollution, and following recommendations from DIN-SPEC 91421. The faecal composts produced will be applied to agricultural fields (rye, buckwheat) prior to sowing according to the existing recommendations for compost fertilisers (max. 510 kg N/ha in 3 years). To fully cover crop N demands, supplemental fertilisation will be done with urine-based fertiliser using state-of-the-art application techniques (i.e. by umbilical injector). In case the P demand is already covered by the faecal compost, the application of urine-based fertiliser will be restricted to avoid excess P fertilisation. The addition of biochar and clay minerals during the composting process contributes to the reduction of N and P leaching and nitrous oxide emissions through the formation of stable organic-mineral complexes. In addition, nutrients bound to it are released slowly during cultivation so that they can be efficiently taken up by the plants.
3. The Spanish pilot will demonstrate a nutrient monitoring tool integrated in the MBR-based RichWater reclamation system. This technological solution will be designed to perform an adequate nutrient balance that takes into account nutrients contained in the effluent of the MBR (i.e. reclaimed water). According to existing literature (1), farmers disregard nutrients in reclaimed water leading to negative environmental impacts and economic losses. Thus, fertilisation and irrigation (fertigation) will be performed according to the crop demand. An experimental test site will be arranged with sub-tropical crops (e.g. avocado and mango trees) in the region of La Axarquía to get on site data. Online nutrient analysis together with the mixing station and soil sensors will allow to adjust the composition of the nutrient solution depending on input nutrient concentrations contained in the reclaimed water and momentary crop needs, according to the growth stage and soil and weather conditions. Thus, the optimal number of fertilisers will be used maximising crop management efficiency and minimising environmental risks.

3 Pilot Regions

The pilot regions in Sweden, Germany, and Spain were chosen because they face similar pressures from nitrogen and phosphorus flows, such as poor chemical and ecological status of water bodies. They also represent different framework conditions along a north-south trajectory, reflecting the heterogeneity of EU regions. Gotland (Sweden) and Malaga (Spain) are comparable in terms of tourism pressure and water scarcity, despite being exposed to very different climates. Lower Saxony (Germany) is vulnerable to fundamental dietary changes due to its large-scale meat industry, which is dependent on international market trends.

These pilot regions exhibit distinct urban-rural interdependencies and territorial scales. They all include urban settlements where nutrients from human excreta are fed into central wastewater treatment systems but are not yet effectively recovered. Surrounding these urban areas are rural regions with intensive agricultural production, which necessitates the use of fertilizers. All three pilot regions are located less than 160 km from coastal zones with high nutrient loads and associated problems such as eutrophication.

Local initiatives in these regions have developed distinct strategies and technological approaches to address the issues caused by linear nutrient flows and to create new value chains based on the efficient and decentralized recycling of nutrients from human excreta. P2GreeN aims to build on these initiatives and their innovative solutions to mainstream circular nutrient flows into the European agri-food system and transfer these newly created value chains to other EU regions. Each regional system offers a suitable solution for circular nutrient flows, building on successfully evaluated technologies and local value chains. However, these technological set-ups are limited by the current governance framework. The immature governance framework inhibits investments in business scale-up and larger value chain innovations. Therefore, further developing this framework will be a key focus of the project.

3.1 Gotland Region, Sweden

The Swedish pilot region of Gotland features a urine-drying system provided by Sanitation360. This portable, off-grid system processes urine on-site in the toilets. It has been optimized and deployed at various locations on Gotland using the existing network and maintenance contracts of mobile toilet provider Touch Down. Key locations include public toilets in the city of Visby and nearby facilities. In the Swedish Pilot, urine serves as a valuable resource collected, processed, and utilized to cultivate barley, subsequently brewed into beer. The technology for producing solid urine fertilizer originated from the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), with Sanitation360 (S360), a spin-off from SLU, established in 2019 to further develop this innovation. In a bid to bolster urine collection efforts and foster a closed-loop system, Touch Down (TD), a local toilet rental company, and Gotland's Bryggeri, a local beer brewer, have partnered to form a circular value chain.

Under the P2GreeN initiative, the goal is to collect 150 m³ of urine by project completion to refine into a dry fertilizer compatible with conventional farming equipment. Present operations are concentrated in Gotland, Uppsala, and Malmö. Over the next three years, expansion plans involve scaling up urine collection efforts to encompass additional regions in Sweden and neighboring countries like Norway. Collection sources encompass both rural and urban areas, inclusive of public and

private buildings, contingent on the installation infrastructure. A key aspect of the project entails the development of methods for removing pharmaceuticals and other toxic substances from urine, ensuring the provision of a quality-assured fertilizer. Consequently, tailoring the urine fertilizer to meet the specific needs of farmers represents a significant focus of the endeavour. In 2023, subcontracted farmers used the pelletized recycling fertilizers in field trials (covering 3-6 hectares) with barley on Gotland. These trials demonstrated a highly effective fertility impact on the crops. The local brewery Gotland Bryggeri is currently validating the suitability of barley grown with urine-based fertilizer for beer production. Within the project timeline, they aim to produce commercially available beer, thereby closing the value chain. The island of Gotland is situated amidst a "dead zone" within the Baltic Sea, a consequence of eutrophication and rising temperatures. In Sweden, over 15,000 tons of nitrogen are discharged annually into the aquatic system by small and municipal wastewater treatment plants, accounting for approximately 30% of total anthropogenic nitrogen emissions. To address this issue, HELCOM's Baltic Sea Action Plan aims to reduce nutrient inputs from wastewater. Gotland faces challenges with old and partially non-functional decentralized sewage treatment plants, exacerbated by high seasonal peaks of nutrient loads from tourism. These discharges impact both groundwater and surface water, necessitating new solutions to enhance nitrogen and phosphorus retention. Support from Science Park Gotland, local NGOs, and government organizations will facilitate source separation and urine drying expansion in Visby, with the technology provided by SLU and S360. The dried urine powder will be delivered to local farmers for barley cultivation, with the harvested product used by GB for beer production in Visby. This initiative creates a new value chain bridging the urban area of Visby with the surrounding rural area, thereby reducing nitrogen and phosphorus loads in wastewater and mitigating pollution in the coastal zone of Gotland.

Field trials conducted by SLU will assess the impact of bio-based urine fertilizer on barley yield, quality, and agro-ecological parameters. Additionally, stakeholders' perceptions and attitudes towards new sanitation systems and technologies will be evaluated to understand the socio-technical system. The knowledge gained from the Gotland region will be instrumental in developing a blueprint for remote areas with high tourism activity.

Figure 2. Gotland's pilot region, value chain scheme

3.2 La Axarquía region, Spain

In the Spanish pilot region of La Axarquía, Bioazul has installed a water reclamation plant to treat and transform municipal wastewater from the wastewater treatment plant of Algarrobo into nutrient-optimized irrigation water for customized agricultural application. TROPS is currently applying the treated water to avocado and mango plots (120 trees total) in an optimized way, supported by a Smart Fertigation Tool, a technology under development by AgriSmart Data. This tool focuses on the smart addition of nutrients tailored to the specific nutritional demands of the crops. This approach adds significant value for producers by promoting the reuse of wastewater resources for crop fertigation. The Axarquía region encompasses a group of municipalities in the province of Málaga, located in Southern Spain, and stands as the primary producer of subtropical crops in Europe. It features a blend of rural areas with robust agricultural activity in the interior and densely populated coastal zones that experience a high influx of tourists, especially during the summer months. However, the region grapples with water scarcity issues, characterized by groundwater overexploitation, depleted water reservoirs, and the looming threat of desertification. Wastewater from various sources, alongside significant nitrogen and phosphorus runoff from agricultural activities, directly flows into the Mediterranean Sea, leading to eutrophication along the coastal zones. Approximately 40% of river waters face potential non-compliance with the European Union's Water Framework Directive (WFD). The circular value chain in the Axarquía pilot region initiates with the collection of sewage from Algarrobo municipality and neighboring areas. This wastewater is then conveyed to the Algarrobo Municipal Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) managed by AXARAGUA, receiving an average influent of 2,150 m³/day (equivalent to 12,247 population equivalents) and with a maximum capacity of 24,000 population equivalents. AXARAGUA, a public company formed by the "Association of Municipalities of the Costa del Sol-Axarquía," oversees not only Algarrobo but also wastewater treatment in Vélez-Málaga, Rincón de la Victoria, Torrox, and Benamocarra municipalities. Upon entry into WWTP, raw wastewater undergoes primary and secondary filtration, sedimentation, and flocculation processes to meet the optimal treatment standards stipulated by European Directive 91/271/EEC. Following secondary treatment, the treated effluent is discharged into the sea through an underwater outfall. Notably, due to the absence of a denitrification process, the nitrogen discharge from the Algarrobo WWTP into the Mediterranean Sea is relatively high, totaling 28.8 tN/year. BIOAZUL oversees the operation of the Water Reclamation Plant as the coordinator of the pilot region.

Within the P2GreeN project, the irrigation system will be enhanced with a nutrient monitoring tool to optimize fertilization practices and prevent over-fertilization of crops irrigated with reclaimed water, thereby advancing its Technology Readiness Level (TRL) from 6 to 8. A decision support system will be collaboratively developed with ASD, a provider of smart irrigation tools. Field trials will be conducted in partnership with local avocado and mango farmers from the TROPS producer association, with agroecological and agronomic impacts monitored by the water research center, CET (WP2). The formulation of regional governance mechanisms will involve close collaboration with local public authorities (AXA, Algarrobo municipality, Málaga province). Wastewater reclamation efforts address the region's vulnerability to

droughts while yielding ecological benefits by reducing the demand for mineral fertilizers and curbing nitrogen, phosphorus, and micropollutant emissions into water bodies, thereby aligning with the objectives of the WFD. This approach holds promise for widespread adoption not only in southern Spain and the Mediterranean region but also in other water-stressed areas across Europe. In the P2GreenN project, facilitating the transferability of this approach involves defining financial considerations related to water reclamation, ensuring compliance with EU Regulation 2020/741 on wastewater reclamation, devising a risk management plan, and formulating a strategic roadmap for expanding reclaimed water usage while fostering societal acceptance. In this context, the Smart Fertigation Tool will serve as a comprehensive solution for monitoring the crucial nutrients and elements in the soil that significantly influence crop development. It facilitates the integration of sensors and transducers embedded in the soil, which gather data on various parameters. Moreover, the tool enables automated management of irrigation and fertilization processes based on real-time data from the plant roots. It will also incorporate information from water sensors installed in the deposit tank containing reclaimed water.

Furthermore, the tool features remote control capabilities to regulate fertilizer dosage and water source mixture automatically, leveraging an integrated Decision Support System (DSS). By analyzing data, the Smart Fertigation Tool can determine whether additional nutrients are required in the reclaimed water, allowing for the incorporation of mineral fertilizers. Additionally, it can assess the necessity of diluting the nutrient-rich effluent with local water sources, primarily groundwater. This intelligent fertigation approach helps prevent excessive nutrient application, thereby reducing the risk of polluting leachates entering water bodies, including nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) emissions into surface and groundwater.

Figure 3. Axarquia's pilot region scheme

3.3 Hamburg- Hannover region, Germany

The German pilot region of Hamburg-Hannover includes the housing cooperative ecovillage Hannover, which plans to install commercially available ceramic urine-diverting flush toilets for 230 residents. They aim to collect approximately 100 m³ of urine per year in cooperation with Goldeimer. The urine will be processed at the

ecovillage in a central facility using the urine treatment system provided by VunaNexus, which will also handle necessary adjustments, operation, and maintenance of the system. The resulting Aurin® fertilizer will be marketed by VunaNexus. These areas face significant nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) pollution in water bodies due to intensive agriculture in rural zones and effluents from urban wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). The river basins of the Elbe and Weser, as well as the coastal areas of the North Sea, are particularly affected, with approximately 90% of water bodies classified as being in moderate to poor ecological and chemical condition. Mitigation measures are necessary to comply with the OSPAR agreement and reduce pollution in the North-East Atlantic. Additionally, groundwater quality is compromised, with nitrate levels exceeding 50 mg N/L due to agricultural runoff. WWTPs remain significant contributors to N and P emissions into aquatic environments, with high energy consumption associated with N and P removal processes. Two pilot cases have been identified in the region. The first case involves the housing cooperative EVH in Hanover, which plans to construct a new city district with 500 dwellings. These dwellings will be equipped with urine-separating flush toilets, allowing for the adsorption of micropollutants and the recovery of nutrients from human excreta. A treatment plant for collected urine will be established and operated at the EVH site by the Swiss technology provider VN, aiming to scale up their Aurin® technology from TRL 6 to TRL 8.

The second pilot case focuses on the establishment of a faecal composting plant in Ollsen, south of Hamburg. GE is active in collecting dry toilet contents and separating urine from various sources in the region. A new composting plant for dry toilet contents will be implemented at the Vagtshoff farm (VH) in Ollsen, using an automated container-based approach developed by Finizio and IGZ. The resulting faecal compost will be applied in field trials at VH to improve soil health and reduce nutrient leaching. Additionally, Aurin® fertilizer produced at EVH will be added as needed to meet crop nitrogen demand. The agronomic and agro-ecological effects of using faecal composts and urine-based fertilizers will be monitored by IGZ.

Overall, the P2GreeN solutions in Lower Saxony will benefit from the lighthouse effect of EVH and the extensive network of GE with other sustainable sanitation initiatives, facilitating the scaling up of these innovative approaches. During the 2023 season, Goldeimer collected dry toilet contents from festivals, allotment gardens, and off-grid nature tourism destinations. A thermophilic container-based composting plant for faeces is being set up, further automating the technology developed by Goldeimer's network partner Finizio. This facility will be operated by Goldeimer on the Vagtshoff farm in Lower Saxony near Hamburg. The Vagtshoff farmers provide industrial waste heat and biochar for the composting facility, as well as agricultural land (6 hectares) for fertilizer application.

Figure 4. Hamburg- Hanover pilot region scheme

The pilot regions in Sweden, Germany and Spain were selected due to the fact that they shared similar challenges related to nitrogen and phosphorous flows, such as the poor chemical and ecological quality of water bodies. The region of Gotland (Sweden) and Malaga (Spain) both experienced tourism pressures and water scarcity, despite having vastly different climates. Lower Saxony (Germany) is vulnerable to fundamental dietary changes due to its large-scale meat industry, which is dependent on international market trends. They all include urban settlements where nutrients from human excreta are fed into central wastewater treatment systems but are not yet effectively recovered. Surrounding these urban areas are rural regions with intensive agricultural production, which necessitates the use of fertilizers. All three pilot regions are located less than 160 km from coastal zones with high nutrient loads and associated problems such as eutrophication.

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3.4 Policy

Despite Sweden's pioneering efforts in developing resource recovery sanitation solutions since the 1990s, the adoption rates of these systems have remained stagnant for decades (Bengtsson & Tillman, 2004; Söderholm et al., 2023). The reasons for this stagnation are multifaceted, including expanded sanitary regulations, a lack of acceptance and awareness of alternative solutions, and the highly centralized nature of the Swedish sanitation system, which presents a significant technological lock-in barrier (Söderholm et al., 2023). Moreover, the governance framework introduces uncertainty for source separation systems due to the absence of explicit definitions for urine, sludge, and wastewater in regulations, complicating their classification. Source-separated fractions, including urine, do not align neatly with existing regulations such as the water and wastewater provision regulation (SFS 2006:412), the sludge

regulation (SNFS 1994:2), or the waste management regulations (SFS 1998:808, SFS 1998:899, and SFS 1998:944). Specifically, the regulation governing the use of plant nutrients in agriculture (SJVFS 2004:62), although explicitly addressing sludge, does not mention human urine (M. Ahlström, personal communication, November 17th, 2023).

In practice, urine is permitted for use in conventional farming in Sweden, allowing S360 to market the urine fertilizer to conventional farmers, who can then legally sell their produce. However, there's a historical aspect to this permission: prior to Sweden's accession to the EU in 1994, urine was also allowed in organic farming. EU membership obligated Sweden to adhere to the EU's regulations for organic farming, which do not permit urine as a fertilizer. In Sweden, another prevalent certification for sustainable farming is KRAV, which could potentially accommodate urine as a fertilizer. However, to become KRAV certified, a farmer in Sweden must first obtain EU organic certification.

As for the Germany pilot region, the primary entry barriers for P2GreeN products revolve around legal compliance and ensuring their safety. Additionally, in the process of transitioning from waste to a qualified resource fit for production, various barriers exist across different sectors and laws. While yellow water collected from sources with less than 50,000 population equivalents appears suitable for nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) recycling as sewage sludge under the CMC regulation, the same cannot be said for contents from dry toilets. Dry toilet contents face hurdles stemming from municipal statutes based on the Water Household Act (WHG §55/56), the Circular Economy Act (BioAbfV §3), and the Fertilizer Act (DüMV Annex II, Table 7). Moreover, there is a lack of guidance for the waste classification of sanitary waste from dry toilets (91/689/EEC; AVV), which contradicts the waste hierarchy principle of Prevention, Reuse, Recycle, Recover, Dispose, as outlined in the federal Circular Economy Act (KrWG §6). The source separation and local treatment of yellow water have not yet been authorized for the Ecovillage Hannover. As a result of these delays, the engineering of the decentralized wastewater system for EVH has been put on hold. However, there have been multiple insights into the Water Household Act and its subordinate rules concerning yellow water. In Germany, the overall technological and legislative approach to sanitary waste strictly encompasses it as wastewater. The updated sewage sludge regulation AbfKlärV 2017, along with its governance framework, is directing stakeholders towards the mono-incineration of sewage sludge, aiming for phosphorus reclamation from ashes. However, this approach compromises the soil-regenerating and nitrogen (N) potentials of sanitary waste. With the recent implementation of Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and the Council dated 25th May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse, a unified European legal framework now exists for all member states. This regulation sets out provisions for the utilization of reclaimed water in agriculture, imposing stringent requirements on water quality and monitoring. However, while this regulation will be directly applicable in each national context, there are numerous existing regulations within the Spanish and Andalusian frameworks that require updating. The implementation of this regulation offers guidance and assurance to farmers and consumers by establishing high water quality standards to adhere to. However, meeting other new obligations, such as the submission of a Risk Management Plan,

presents challenges. Addressing this challenge is a key focus within P2GreenN, as one of our governance solutions includes the preparation of a Risk Mitigation Plan for the Axarquía pilot. A revision of the current Spanish regulation on water reuse (i.e., Royal Decree 1620/2007) is imperative to align with the provisions of Regulation (EU) 2020/741. Additionally, procedures for granting licenses to users of reclaimed water must be adapted to the new situation by the regional government of Andalusia and water basin authorities, which hold the authority for licensing water reuse permits. National and regional actors must collaborate to conduct a comprehensive revision of the existing legal framework.

4. Feasibility Studies

Italy

In Italy, the highway station provider Chef Express is considering implementing urine separation and collection in their toilets to produce fertilizer using VN's treatment system. This innovative approach would enable the creation of urine-based liquid fertilizer, which could then be marketed in small bottles directly at the service stations. Additionally, the Finagricola agricultural cooperative in Campania is exploring the possibility of using BioA's RichWater technology to irrigate and fertilize crops with treated wastewater sourced from the municipality of Battipaglia. However, they are also open to the idea of utilizing fertilizer produced from source-separated urine. This demonstrates a growing interest in sustainable agricultural practices and the utilization of alternative resources within the Italian agricultural sector.

Hungary

In Hungary, the feasibility study aims to thoroughly analyse how P2GreenN's solutions can be effectively implemented within the Eastern European context. This study will also identify potential partners who can contribute to forming a Hungarian follower region. The key components of the feasibility study include:

(i) Analysis of national and regional policies and regulations: This will involve a comprehensive examination of existing policies and regulations related to water management, wastewater treatment, and agricultural practices in Hungary.

(ii) Identification of relevant institutional/governance framework and funding pathways: This aspect of the study will focus on identifying the key institutions, stakeholders, and governance structures involved in water and agriculture sectors in Hungary. Additionally, potential funding sources and pathways for implementing P2GreenN solutions will be explored.

(iii) Analysis of technical, economic, and social aspects relevant for implementation: This will entail assessing the technical feasibility, economic viability, and social acceptance of implementing P2GreenN solutions in Hungary. Factors such as technological adaptability, cost-effectiveness, and societal attitudes towards sustainable water management practices will be evaluated.

The study aims to identify three suitable sites for replicating different technological approaches from the pilot regions and initiate the transfer of project results at the conclusion of the P2GreenN project. This process will facilitate the dissemination and

adoption of innovative water reuse and resource recovery solutions in Hungary, contributing to sustainable development in the region.

France

In this follower region the City of Paris has already started the transition into the block of buildings in Saint-Vincent-de-Paul. More specifically, the building of Chauffeured has already started the process of implementing storage of collection and recycling of urine. The work began in 2021 and should be completed in 2027. The wastewater transport networks, and that for urine, were built in 2021/2022. The buildings of the different lots will be built gradually from 2024. The urine treatment plant should be built in 2025. The case study of this follower region is going to work as a preliminary stage and as reference point to the development of the feasibility studies in the other follower regions. City of Paris will give the opportunity to the P2Green partners to extract important results on social-economic level.

4.1 Greece

As part of the project, Greece is one of the four follower regions. The Greek follower region, under the leadership of Centre for Research and Technology in Greece, will be divided into three distinct case studies. These studies will evaluate the implementation of various technologies in different contexts to ascertain their feasibility and potential impact.

4.1.1 T.O.E. V Tavropou

The first case study will be conducted in T.O.E.V Tavropou in the city of Karditsa. This is the local land reclamation organization that plays a crucial role in managing irrigation of more than 114.750 acres and water resources in the region of Karditsa. The water supply of this organization is provided by the water reservoir of Lake Plastira through the hydroelectric power station. The water supply is regulated in a 600.000 cubic meter capacity reforming reservoir located at an altitude of more than 188.10 meters which gives the main advantage of the surface network where it doesn't require energy consumption for the transport and distribution of water. The organization is responsible for irrigating 92.156 acres of cultivated area with the main crops being cotton and maize, which are two high water demanding crops.

Based on the latest data from T.O.E.V. Tavropou, the maximum discharge of the irrigational area is 16 cubic meters per second, with the main disadvantage being reduced water efficiency. More specifically, for the irrigation period 2023 the organization of TOEV Tavropou managed irrigation adjusting its water management practices in response to these challenges since the amount of water of Lake Plastira was reduced by 30%. Apart from the water reduction Greece in general is facing droughts and water scarcity especially in the agricultural areas. For this reason, the decision was made to conduct the first feasibility study in this area in collaboration with the irrigation organization focusing on assessing the barriers and challenges of the implementation of BioAzul's RichWater technology, which involves irrigating and fertilizing nearby agricultural fields with treated municipal wastewater.

As for the technical part, the installation of Bioazul technology will be in the existing Wastewater Treatment Plant of Karditsa, as it is shown in the figure below. The main reason is minimise the expanses of installing the technology and also to get advantage of the amount of water that the WWTP uses.

Figure 5. Wastewater Treatment Plant in Karditsa.

Additionally, in order to recognize the barriers and the challenges of implementing this technology in Greece, CERTH organized a focus group where experts (agronomists, soil scientists, biobased fertilizers representatives, professors) where participated. Based on this focus group the current technology was recognized as an innovative idea demonstrating significant potential, especially when integrated with advanced monitoring techniques. As for the robustness of the technology, it was at a high level reflecting its reliability, however further efforts are required to stabilize the properties of organic material to ensure consistent performance. Also, the level of adoption of technology and outcomes was recognized as high enough but to enhance the adoption rates it is crucial to align the technology with the needs of farmers in the current area.

4.1.2 Agricultural University of Athens

The second case study will take place at the Agricultural University of Athens. Research will be conducted in a renovated three-story building to evaluate the implementation of Vuna Nexus technology in existing toilet systems. For this case study, the installation will be in the basement of the building and will be connected with all the toilet pipelines to utilize all the wastewater. The main objective of this implementation is to utilize the resulting fertilizer in the university's agricultural fields to see the level of effectiveness of the liquid biobased fertilizer.

Additionally, based on the focus group that was conducted the Vona Nexus technology offers moderate potential for innovation. The experts highlighted its suitability for implementation in organized settings like the building that was selected. This environment provides the necessary scale and organizational for efficient application. As for the robustness of the technology was in a high level reflecting moderate reliability and through further development will upscale the stability and adaptability of this technology. Experts raised critical concerns about its implementation, particularly

the environmental impact of producing chemical fertilizers. While technology offers a potential alternative, its feasibility compared to existing systems requires further investigation. For instance, determining whether it is more advantageous to renovate or construct new buildings with advanced features like three separate pipeline networks is crucial for assessing long-term practicality and cost-effectiveness.

4.1.3 Toilet renting company

For the third feasibility study, a partnership has been established with a toilet renting company that services festivals in the city of Athens. The aim is to demonstrate the implementation of sustainable toilet technologies and establish a twinning relationship between the pilot region and the following region. This twinning initiative is intended to facilitate the scaling up of the technology's impact.

The main objective of this collaboration is to understand the way a toilet renting company is processing with the sanitary waste that collects through the different festivals and activities that covers. In the early stages of the feasibility study, data were collected concerning the amounts of waste waters this company is processing depending on the activity. Also, this study focuses on understanding the company's current waste management systems, logistical framework and customers' needs. By analyzing the volume and composition of wastewater collected during various activities, we will identify the potential for integrating Goldeimer's technology to process and repurpose these waste streams efficiently. The goal is to explore how this technology can enhance the sustainability of their operations, reduce environmental impact, and create value through the production of bio-based fertilizers. This collaboration will also assess the scalability and practicality of deploying the technology in diverse event scenarios, providing insights for future adoption and integration across similar operations in the industry.

Conclusions

P2GreeN's has already completed the second year successfully extracting important results both in the pilot regions and the follower regions. The feasibility studies have already started in all the follower regions with the help of the interested stakeholders. Additionally, the project is an indicator of a pioneer effort to advance the circular nutrient flows by integrating these innovative technologies, policy engagement and stakeholders' collaboration. By using these technologies where the human sanitary waste is converting into a safe, biobased fertilizers P2GreeN addresses critical environmental challenges contributing to the EU's sustainability goals.

The three pilot regions in Sweden, Germany and Spain and the studied that have been developed, have demonstrated the feasibility and the potential of these technologies in different environmental and socio-economic parameters. The ongoing feasibility studies in Italy, Hungary, France, and Greece are expanding the project's impact, adapting solutions to regional needs, and fostering scalable and transferable governance models. Despite challenges such as implementation costs and policy alignment, the strong support from stakeholders underscores the promise of bio-based fertilizers as a viable alternative to conventional chemical inputs.

The holistic approach of P2GreeN and the main goal is to encompass these

technological advancements, the stakeholder's collaboration and the policy initiatives in order to mark a significant leap to establish sustainable food systems in Europe. The knowledge and experience gained through this project will pave the way for scaling these technologies across the EU, fostering resilience and supporting the transition to a sustainable circular economy.

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